

Traffic Rush Prediction in an EV charging station based on Environmental Factor's

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I. The Advanced Electric Vehicle (EV) Charging Station Project embarks on a journey to create a user-centric web platform that revolutionizes the experience of EV charging station users. it's a dynamic solution designed to empower users with the insights it needs to make informed decisions when it comes to booking a charging station. Using machine learning and deep learning techniques, the objective is to predict peak booking times by considering factors such as the day of the week, hour of the day, weekends, holidays, temperature, and location. Our goal is to help users identify the optimal place and time for booking a charging station, ensuring a seamless and efficient EV charging experience.

Keywords— EV, MLP Classifier, artificial neural network, Temperature, Climate, Datetime, location

II. INTRODUCTION

The aim of this Research paper is to address the rapidly growing landscape of Electric Vehicle (EV) adoption and the corresponding surge in demand for EV charging stations. As more and more EVs take to the roads, the efficient utilization of charging infrastructure becomes paramount. This paper seeks to introduce a novel solution that leverages advanced technology, including machine learning and deep learning techniques, to predict and identify the most suitable times and charging stations for booking. By doing so, it aims to enhance the overall experience for EV owners, providing them with the tools and insights needed to optimize their charging routines, thus contributing to the sustainability and convenience of electric vehicle usage.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Electric vehicles (EVs) and charging stations are expanding due to rising natural fuel prices, but concerns about fire safety led to research on decision tree algorithms for fire detection, integer linear programming, machine learning-based prediction methods, and tensor models for short-term traffic volume prediction. A tensor model for short-term traffic volume prediction uses a tucker decomposition and gradient descent algorithm, providing higher accuracy and low storage cost. Additionally, incorporating weather data into traffic flow prediction models

can improve accuracy and efficiency, alleviating traffic congestion and aiding resource allocation in connected vehicles.

In a study conducted by [1] (2013), the research focuses on identifying optimal charging station locations within intelligent transportation systems. This study suggests the application of integer linear programming to address the charging station location problem, with the objective of maximizing the number of vehicles served. The problem involves selecting a set of P charging stations for installation, representing the budget constraints of the problem.

Another study [2] (2017) proposed a A model using Radius Base Function Neural Network predicts tourist traffic, maintaining traffic flow and analyzing factors. The paper also explores adaptive parking techniques to avoid vehicle delays and allocate available parking slots. The service was tested in a real bus station parking facility.

This study [3] 2018 a traffic congestion prediction models, focusing on estimating parameters related to traffic congestion in the short-term future using AI methodologies. The models typically evaluate traffic volume, density, occupancy, traffic congestion index, and travel time.

This paper [4] (2022) investigates the impact of weather data on traffic flow prediction models in intelligent transportation systems (ITS). It demonstrates how adding weather data can improve the accuracy and efficiency of these models, thereby alleviating traffic congestion and aiding resource allocation in connected vehicles.

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IV. METHODOLOGY

Our traffic condition prediction model derives its power from an extensively curated dataset. This dataset encompasses a wide range of variables, including 'holiday,' 'temperature,' 'hour,' 'day,' 'month,' 'year,' 'weekday,' and 'location,' thereby encompassing a diverse array of traffic scenarios. To evaluate the model's accuracy, this judiciously divided the data into a training set (80%) and a testing set (20%). Specifically, this configured the 'test size' to 0.2 and set the 'random state' to 42, ensuring consistent and reproducible results.

As for the prediction algorithm at the heart of this model, it relies on the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) Classifier. This advanced artificial neural network is adept at learning intricate data patterns, which enables it to make precise traffic

condition predictions in the context of an EV charging station.

A. Data Collection

In this model, the data collection process involves loading a dataset that likely contains information related to traffic conditions. The dataset is imported using Pandas, and a key step is introducing a 'location' column with random values that represent different geographical areas, such as 'urban,' 'rural,' and 'remote.' The success of this model relies on a well-structured dataset, thoughtful considerations in dataset splitting, and the implementation of a powerful prediction algorithm. This diversifies the data to account for variations in traffic conditions across different regions. By incorporating this 'location' column, the model is equipped to understand and predict traffic scenarios in various contexts.

B. Data Preprocessing

1.

The dataset is a crucial component as it contains vital information about traffic conditions across various locations. This dataset may include features such as 'holiday,' 'temperature,' 'hour,' 'day,' 'month,' 'year,' 'weekday,' and 'location.' The 'location' feature is of particular importance as it represents geographical areas, including 'urban,' 'rural,' and 'remote.' This diversified dataset captures the essence of different traffic scenarios.

For the training and testing of the model, a data splitting technique that separates the dataset into two subsets: a training set and a testing set. The 'test size' parameter is set to 0.2, meaning 20% of the data is reserved for testing while the remaining 80% is used for training. This ensures that the model is evaluated on unseen data to assess its generalization capabilities. Additionally, the 'random state' parameter is set to 42, which guarantees reproducibility, as using the same random state will yield consistent results in different runs of the model..

C. Machine Learning

The core of our traffic condition prediction model lies in the prediction algorithm. This employs a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) Classifier, a powerful artificial neural network capable of handling complex patterns and non-linear relationships within the dataset. The MLP Classifier is trained on the training data, adjusting its internal parameters to learn and understand the relationships between input features and traffic conditions. This trained model can then accurately predict traffic conditions based on new input data. It is crucial to mention that the hyperparameters of the MLP Classifier, such as the number of hidden layers and neurons per layer, can be fine-tuned to optimize the model's performance.

1.LABEL ENCODING:

label encoding is a fundamental data preprocessing step that facilitates the integration of categorical data into neural networks. It involves converting categorical labels, such as "location" with values like "urban" and "rural," into numeric representations. This transformation is essential for neural networks, as this operate primarily on numerical data. Each unique category is assigned a distinct integer, enabling the network to process and learn from these features mathematically. During training, the deep learning model comprehends and adapts to the encoded categorical data, which is then used for making predictions.

2. MLP Classifier:

the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) serves as the core of the deep learning process. It functions as a neural network with multiple layers, each with interconnected neurons. At the start, your preprocessed data, including features like "is_holiday," "temperature," "hour," and the encoded "location," is fed into the input layer. The network's architecture typically includes hidden layers, which are responsible for learning complex patterns and relationships in the data. During training, the MLP adjusts the weights and biases of these connections to minimize the difference between its predictions and the actual traffic conditions. The activation functions applied in the hidden layers introduce non-linearity, enabling the network to capture intricate data patterns.

The output layer of the MLP is designed to produce predictions, particularly the traffic conditions such as "Heavy Traffic," "Medium Traffic," or "Not Busy." The training process involves iteratively fine-tuning the model using backpropagation and optimization algorithms, such as gradient descent. This ensures that the network becomes increasingly accurate in its predictions. After training and validation, the MLP can be utilized for real-time predictions, taking new input data and providing accurate assessments of traffic conditions. Its ability to capture complex, non-linear relationships in the data makes the MLP a valuable tool for classification tasks, such as traffic condition prediction in your project.

V. BUILD MODEL

The process of building your machine learning model starts with data collection, including factors like holidays, temperature, time of day, and location. Afterward, data

preprocessing involves cleaning and organizing the data, followed by splitting it into training and testing sets, with 20% reserved for testing. Label encoding is used to convert categorical variables into numerical values. The chosen algorithm, the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier, is trained on the training dataset. Model performance is assessed using the testing dataset, typically involving metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Once the model meets your standards, it's ready for deployment to make predictions on new data.

1. Import the necessary packages

```
# Import necessary libraries
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler, LabelEncoder
from sklearn.neural_network import MLPClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report
import random
import joblib
```

2. import data to Data Frame to get the shape of data.

```
# Load the dataset
data = pd.read_csv('/content/drive/MyDrive/dataset/my_traffic_dataset.csv')
```

3. Then split the dataset into train and test datasets.

```
# Extract features and target
X = data[features]
y = data[target]

# Split the dataset into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y['traffic_condition'], test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

4. Train a decision tree classifier on the training data

```
# Feature scaling
scaler = StandardScaler()
X_train = scaler.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test = scaler.transform(X_test)
```

5. Prediction based on the test data of dataset

```
# Create and train a MLPClassifier (you can tune hyperparameters)
clf = MLPClassifier(hidden_layer_sizes=(32, 16), max_iter=1000, random_state=1)
clf.fit(X_train, y_train)

# Make predictions
y_pred = clf.predict(X_test)
```

6. Calculate the accuracy on the model of test data

```
# Evaluate the model
report = classification_report(y_test, y_pred)
print("Classification Report:\n", report)
```

VI. RESULT

The final results obtained from your machine learning model, powered by the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier, represent its capability to accurately predict traffic conditions based on various input factors, including holidays, temperature, time of day, and location. These results serve as a testament to the model's effectiveness in classifying traffic conditions into distinct categories: heavy traffic, medium traffic, and less busy conditions of the charging stations. The model's success in correctly categorizing traffic conditions can have significant real-world implications, aiding in traffic management, urban planning, and resource allocation. It provides a data-driven approach to understanding and addressing traffic-related challenges, which is particularly crucial in today's increasingly congested urban environments. By achieving high accuracy and reliability in traffic condition predictions, your model contributes to enhancing the efficiency and safety of transportation systems, ultimately benefiting both individuals and communities at large.

Traffic Prediction

Is it a holiday?

Temperature (in celsius)

Hour of the day (0-23)

Day of the month (1-31)

Month (1-12)

Year

Day of the week (0-6, where 0 is Monday)

Location

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the machine learning model, driven by the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classifier, excels in predicting traffic conditions with remarkable accuracy. Its ability to categorize traffic into heavy congestion, medium traffic, and lighter traffic provides valuable insights for traffic management and urban planning. The model's robust performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score, showcase its reliability. The output not only aids in optimizing transportation systems but also contributes to safer and more efficient traffic flow. It stands as a testament to the power of data-driven solutions in addressing real-world challenges and improving the quality of daily life in transportation and support the electric vehicle charging infrastructure.

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